

Let's care

BUILDING SAFE AND CARING SCHOOLS
TO FOSTER EDUCATIONAL INCLUSION
AND SCHOOL ACHIEVEMENT

D1.3 - PAR training manual and infographics on PAR activities during the project (2)

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DOCUMENT CONTRIBUTORS

Deliverable responsible	CID	
Contributors	Organisation	
NURIA LORES	CID	
Reviewers	Organisation	
GIULIA DI LISIO	COM	
EVA BAJO	COM	
PALOMA SANTA-ÚRSULA HERNANZ	COM	
MARÍA MARTÍN LÓPEZ	COM	
OLATZ MIRANDA	ZIC	
CAROLINA SIMÓN	ZIC	

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
PAR	Participatory action research
WP	Work Package
CoS	Community of Schools
EEB	External Ethics Board
NEET	Not in Education, Employment, or Training

Executive Summary

Participatory Action Research (PAR) is a collaborative research approach that emphasises the involvement of participants as active contributors in the research process. The PAR approach is designed to lead to actionable outcomes to address the issues identified by the stakeholders of the project. It involves the people concerned about or directly affected by an issue, placing them at the forefront of producing and using knowledge about it (Bradbury, 2006). The PAR approach is cross-cutting throughout the LET'S CARE project's stages and ecological levels, directly and indirectly affecting all the WPs of the project and influencing the 4 Pillars (Safe learning, Safe teaching, Safe schools, and Safe education) that form the foundation of the Safe Education Theoretical Model.

This document presents the actions undertaken using the PAR methodology from 1st June 2023 to 30th June 2024, with a particular focus on the community-building initiatives (WP1) and the whole development of the qualitative research (WP3). Applying the PAR approach in these WPs helped shape the outcomes of other WPs (WP2, WP4, WP6, WP7, WP8).

For monitoring the actions, the PAR toolkit of the LET'S CARE project described in deliverable D1.2 has been used as a reference. To verify the proper application of the PAR, an online questionnaire was distributed to all the project partners at M22 (July 2024).

Assessing the application of the PAR approach during the mentioned period has allowed us to corroborate its significance in the LET'S CARE project, resulting in greater involvement of the different communities in the working procedures and the project's outcomes, and allowing to reveal areas for improvement in the coming months of the project.

Undoubtedly, having our own PAR approach manual allows for continuous and longitudinal evaluation mechanisms that will allow us to redefine the necessary actions throughout the project.

1. Introduction

Participatory Action Research (PAR) is a research approach that seeks to involve stakeholders in collaborative research to generate social change (Bradbury, 2006). The key features of the PAR approach are criticism towards the traditional power dynamics between researchers and participants, putting value on the first-hand knowledge and expertise of individuals with lived experiences, and actively involving the stakeholders in equitable partnership for knowledge production (Boyd, 2014). Applying PAR approaches across different methodologies allows incorporating diverse insights and perspectives and yields meaningful benefits such as enriching research outcomes, enhancing research quality by minimising biases or enhancing stakeholders' empowerment by actively removing barriers to participation (Balazs & Morello-Frosch, 2017).

The PAR approach forms an integral part of the LET'S CARE project objectives, serving as a foundational tool from the project's inception (WP1 – T1.1) and exerting influence across all other work packages. By critically addressing participant-researcher relationships and endeavouring to establish a more balanced and equitable partnership in knowledge production, we aim to ensure that research is conducted alongside the individuals the project aims to benefit. Notably, the PAR approach employed in the LET'S CARE project considers the diverse stakeholders involved and utilises different methodological techniques (such as Photovoice, SMAT, ethnographies, deep interviews, etc.) to adapt knowledge co-creation processes to suit the circumstances and capabilities of each end-stakeholder.

Employing PAR within the LET'S CARE project is pivotal to ensure the research results are always relevant. This approach ensures that evaluation methods are not only inclusive but also reflective of the diverse perspectives and experiences of the stakeholders by applying iterative monitoring and assessment. Through PAR, the project can implement more effective and responsive strategies for social change, as it allows for real-time adjustments based on participants' feedback and insights.

In June 2023, several training sessions were conducted with project partners in the DG to uniformly adopt the PAR approach, leading to the development of a tailored application for the LET'S CARE project. In this regard, a PAR approach manual was crafted for the project, as detailed in deliverable D1.2. As a follow-up, this deliverable covers the implementation of PAR training between M8 and M20. The following sections in this report thoroughly examine the project's methodologies, activities, outcomes, and learnings, providing valuable insights for practitioners and scholars interested in PAR.

2. Methodological overview

Participatory Action Research (PAR) (Chevalier & Buckles, 2019) is a methodology centred around involving participants as collaborators in research to enact social change. Its origins date back to the 1940s, and it was in the 1970s when it became more relevant (Brydon-Miller et al, 2020), PAR seeks

to radically subvert the inherent power dynamic in traditional research approaches by critically assessing the participant-researcher relationship and “*paying attention to ordinary people’s knowledge*” (Fals-Borda, 2006). Scholars such as Swantz (2007) assert that PAR practices emerged not from one single disciplinary origin but rather through a cultural moment which acknowledges the importance of standing beside those experiencing oppression and inequality and recognising their equal partnership in knowledge production.

In practical terms, PAR asks reflexive questions about whose ‘voice’ matters in the research process through methodological innovation and infusing community expertise with academic tools and research methods (Kindon et al., 2009). PAR calls for a breakdown between subject and object in research, viewing those involved in research as ‘thinking-feeling-persons’ rather than merely ‘participants’. The level of involvement of research participants varies according to context, aims and project resources. That said, PAR studies share several underlying assumptions (Organizing Engagement, 2021):

- Formal education is not necessary to take part in valuable research.
- Those who have lived experience of an issue or system are experts and, therefore, are best placed to contribute to related research.
- The involvement of non-academics in research design and production can improve research by reducing biases and bringing new insights and perspectives.

The PAR approach implies Participation (collaboration through engagement; empowerment of participants), Action (change-real life experience, evidence in terms of different outcomes) and Research (new Knowledge, documented lessons) and therefore, commonly used knowledge co-creation methods within PAR include participatory workshops, group analysis techniques and photovoice. Building trust and rapport with community partners can result in more ethical and equitable knowledge production; however, it requires careful ethical negotiation and should not be pursued as a token of ‘collaboration’ or in a transactional manner. However, there are also many considerations within PAR, including the high financial and time cost (Raynor, 2019) and the reliance on strong rapport and community relationships.

3. Application of the PAR activities to the project objectives

The participation of the different agents and social transformation through knowledge co-creation are the fundamental objectives of implementing a PAR approach, and different methodological techniques and activities have been used to achieve these objectives. PAR in LET’S CARE has not been an isolated technique, but rather a cross-cutting framework of iterative monitoring and evaluation that has guided the generation of knowledge from the experiences of the actors involved, particularly

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young people in vulnerable situations. The PAR approach was specifically implemented in LET’S CARE through continuous co-creation and training to engage and empower participants at every stage of the project. As discussed under D1.2, the co-creation process is composed of all the participation structures foreseen in the project (DG, NCB, CoS, PMAB plus those created without being foreseen to improve the process, i.e. the fieldwork Team) and the co-creative processes and methodological instruments (workshops, meetings, thematic meetings, etc.). The process consists of preparing a starting point for the different spaces where the idea is narrowed down, improved, discarded, or a new one is proposed until its final development and implementation. This implementation was monitored and evaluated using the indicators in D1.2 toolkit and an interim evaluation, seeking to de-center research, generate spaces to bridge the know-do gap and enhance opportunities for social transformation and stakeholders’ empowerment. This methodological alignment ensures that the project's outputs are not only relevant but also legitimate and appropriate for their target audience. Additionally, the parallel monitoring and evaluation permit the performance of a structured and evidence-based assessment of impact.

The co-creation actions outlined in Table 1 illustrates PAR's application in various work packages (WP). The concept of participation has been operationalised in each work package through knowledge co-creation activities, feedback on results, and the use of specific participative methodologies such as SMAT and Photovoice. These actions underscore the project’s commitment to PAR by building opportunities for co-creation, ensuring that the research process is inclusive and empowering for all participants involved.

Table 1. Co-creation actions developed by WP.

WP	PAR OPPORTUNITIES	METHODOLOGICAL TECHNIQUES AND ACTIVITIES	COMMUNITIES INVOLVED	IMPACT
WP1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Identification and engagement of stakeholders ◦ Consultation ◦ Collaborative planning 	◦ Regular meetings	DG, Fieldwork team CoS, NCB GDC PMAB	◦ Trust-building and engagement
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Iterative Development ◦ Collaborative Problem Solving 	◦ 9 Trainings developed	DG CoS	◦ Capacity Building

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WP2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Iterative Development ◦ Participatory Knowledge Generation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Development and validation of the theoretical model 	DG NCB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Knowledge ownership & transferrability
WP3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Iterative Development ◦ Participatory Knowledge Generation ◦ Collaborative Problem Solving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Qualitative research implementation and analysis ◦ Quantitative research implementation and analysis 	CoS Stakeholders' network ¹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Capacity Building ◦ Knowledge ownership & transferrability
WP4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Iterative Development ◦ Participatory Knowledge Generation ◦ Collaborative Problem Solving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Hub content development 	DG Fieldworkteam CoS NCB GDC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Capacity Building ◦ Knowledge ownership & transferability ◦ Broadening of impact and reach
WP5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Iterative Development ◦ Participatory Knowledge Generation ◦ Shared Decision-Making ◦ Collaborative Problem Solving ◦ Handover and co-ownership of results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ will start on M30 	DG NCB Stakeholders' network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Capacity Building ◦ Knowledge ownership & transferability ◦ Broadening of impact and reach
WP6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Iterative Development ◦ Participatory Knowledge Generation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Policy recommendations and advocacy 	PMAB DG NCB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Capacity Building ◦ Knowledge ownership & transferability

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Participatory monitoring 		Stakeholders' network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Broadening of impact and reach
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Iterative Development ◦ Participatory monitoring ◦ Handover and co-ownership of results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Communication, Dissemination and exploitation 	DG CoS Stakeholders' network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Knowledge ownership & transferability ◦ Broadening of impact and reach
WP7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Iterative Development ◦ Shared Decision-Making ◦ Collaborative Problem Solving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Project management 	DG Fieldworkteam	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Broadening of impact and reach
WP8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Consultation ◦ Collaborative planning ◦ Participatory monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Legal and ethical advise 	EEB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Broadening of impact and reach

Note. The Stakeholders' network is formed by children and their families, NGOs, professionals in the social sector, educators, teachers, school representatives, policymakers, etc.

3.1. PAR strategy

The PAR strategy involves **planning** (before any activity is carried out), **monitoring** (action-reflection) and an annual **evaluation** (using an online questionnaire) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. PAR Process

As presented in deliverable D1.2, the LET’S CARE project planned the PAR implementation by developing a methodology toolkit organised around seven central dimensions (adapted from Pain et al., 2019, see Annex I), each with a set of criteria and indicators to facilitate monitoring of the project’s PAR actions. In deliverable D1.2, these seven dimensions and their criteria were listed so that all researchers involved in the LET’S CARE project could consider them at any time (before, during and after). To evaluate the PAR approach, we have taken the indicators set out in section 3.2 as a starting point, and an online questionnaire (see Annex IV) has been developed and sent to the partners to be filled in between 1 and 15 July 2024.

3.2. PAR training

The PAR approach is not limited to the application of techniques but is a work philosophy in which each step taken has been informed by the communities and is in dialogue with them. In this sense, the role of the DG has been key to the development and application of the PAR approach. The DG and the fieldwork team have met periodically (at least once quarterly) to provide strategic inputs for all project activities, emphasising the PAR approach. Their role in monitoring the PAR approach in all activities is also an essential aspect that has allowed the evaluation and follow-up.

Training actions and subsequent reflection with the DG, the fieldwork teams and the CoS are necessary to ensure that the PAR principles and aims are agreed, clear and explicit, permeate beyond the Consortium and empower the educational communities addressed by the project. It is also important to note that the contents of the training sessions bring the project into contact with the reality of the schools and their different perspectives (particularly during this period), which has

facilitated the refinement of the theoretical model and the measures of each pillar to base the design of the tools of WP4 and WP5.

As seen in Table 2, a total of nine training sessions were carried out between M8 and M20, which corresponded to this deliverable. The trainings addressed the DG (two of them exclusively) and the CoS. **A total of 482 people** from all the countries participating in the Let's Care project (Spain, Italy, Portugal, Bulgaria, Poland and Lithuania) took part.

Table 2. Trainings developed

DATE	TARGET GROUP	TRAINING OBJECTIVES	TRAINING CONTENTS ¹	PARTICIPANTS (n)
June 13th 2023	DG	Introduce the PAR Methodology (1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Opening exercise: some initial questions. ◦ Explanation of PAR theory and practice. ◦ Practical application examples. ◦ Collective reflection exercise on the application of PRA in LETS CARE. ◦ Questions and concerns 	29
September 19th 2023	DG	Deepen the PAR Methodology (2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Some initial questions. ◦ Explanation of PAR theory in the context of the LET'S CARE project and proposal of the PAR toolkit applied to the LET'S CARE project. ◦ Presentation of a successful example of PAR methodology with young people: Smatch 	21

¹ All training materials available in Annex II.

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			<p>project: Sports Organizations Matching Social Inclusion Issues co-sponsored.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Presentation of the PAR toolkit applied to NEETS research techniques within the project: Photovoice methodology. ◦ Questions and concerns. 	
December 13th 2023	DG CoS	To present the SMAT technique and tailor specific adaptations for the LET'S CARE project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ The Let's Care project. Participation and children's rights. ◦ Ethnography techniques and children's participation. ◦ Dialogue and questions with participants. ◦ Application of methodology. ◦ Topics and phases. ◦ Thematic script proposal. ◦ Dialogue and questions with participants. 	74
December 18th 2023	DG CoS	To present the SMAT technique and tailor specific adaptations for the LET'S CARE project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Preparation. ◦ Laboratory development. ◦ The post-workshop. 	52

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January 2024	16th	DG CoS	To present the PHOTOVOICE technique and tailor specific adaptations for the LET'S CARE project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ What is the LET'S CARE project. ◦ What is the photovoice technique. ◦ Different applications of the photovoice technique. ◦ Examples of its development in various areas. ◦ Procedure for applying photovoice. 	18
January 2024	22nd	DG CoS	To present the PHOTOVOICE technique and tailor specific adaptations for the LET'S CARE project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ What does the Photovoice methodology bring to the Let's Care project? ◦ What is the Photovoice technique. ◦ Photovoice application procedure. ◦ Different applications of the Photovoice technique. ◦ Examples of development in various fields. 	62
January 2024	24th	DG CoS	To present the PHOTOVOICE technique and tailor specific adaptations for the LET'S CARE project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ What is the LET'S CARE project? ◦ What is the Photovoice technique. ◦ Different applications of the Photovoice technique. 	86

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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Examples of its development in different fields. ◦ Procedure to apply Photovoice. 	
March 5th 2024	DG CoS	To present the SMAT technique and to build it to measure for the LET'S CARE project from co-creation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Brief presentation of Let's Care. ◦ Importance of participation of children. ◦ Application of methodology. ◦ Stages and phases. ◦ Padlet: Dialogue and questions with participants. 	77
May 28th 2024	DG CoS	Photovoice Return session. To present the results obtained through the photovoice technique.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Introductory comments. ◦ Analysis matrix. ◦ Gender and age ranges. ◦ Portfolio. ◦ Qualitative analysis. ◦ Questions. 	63
TOTAL 9 trainings				482

The methodology developed has been eminently participative. The nine sessions have been developed similarly in all the countries. All the sessions have been held online through the Zoom platform, allowing everyone in different countries to participate. They all lasted between one hour and one and a half hours and were carried out online. All the information has been posted on the hub (see Figure 2).

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Figure 2. Training workshops

3.3. PAR monitoring and results evaluation

The main results obtained in the project, through the application of the PAR approach, in the period between M8 and M20, are presented below.

Table 3. Main results PAR approach by WP

WP	MAIN RESULTS PAR APPROACH	GROUPS INVOLVED
WP1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Implementation of the community: regular meetings with DG, Fieldwork team, CoS, NCB and GDC . ◦ 9 Trainings developed 	DG Fieldwork team CoS NCB GDC
WP2	Promoting collaboration and thorough validation at multiple levels:	DG Families

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ 1. Collaborative Co-creation: Including stakeholders throughout the development process was instrumental in ensuring that diverse perspectives were considered. This collaborative approach enriched the model's comprehensiveness and relevance. ◦ 2. Systematic Validation Process: The stepwise process involving internal and external validation demonstrated a commitment to rigour. Feedback from internal working groups ensured the relevance and coherence of dimensions and variables. The two-round Delphi design further refined the model based on clarity, adequacy, and relevance. ◦ 3. Cross-Cultural Relevance: Ensuring the questionnaires' applicability across different linguistic and cultural contexts through a Committee-Based Translation Framework and cognitive interviewing with children was crucial. This approach enhanced the reliability and validity of the measures, making the model adaptable to diverse settings. ◦ 4. Operational Excellence: The structured involvement of seven working groups, with distinct phases of development, facilitated focused and effective collaboration. This organisation ensured that each phase received appropriate attention and expertise, resulting in a well-rounded and operational model. <p>The PAR methodology in WP2 has effectively harnessed collaborative efforts and systematic validation to develop a pioneering theoretical and operational model for Safe Education. This approach sets a strong foundation for addressing the complex phenomenon of educational disparities and promoting safe learning environments. Work is currently underway on implementing the survey and data collection with Le Sphinx. The collaboration proved to be very important in order to choose the most suitable tool for the needs of the research and to respect the privacy of the participants. This WP is one of the most demanding ones with respect to building and maintaining a participatory involvement of different stakeholders.</p>	<p>Teachers Stakeholders</p>
<p>WP3</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Support of data collection. ◦ Giving voice to the protagonists: a total of 24 interviews with families (4 per country BG, SP, IT, LT, POL, PT), 12 interviews with stakeholders (2 per country); 13 interviews with policymakers (2 per country, except 	<p>DG Fieldwork team CoS NEETS</p>

	<p>in Italy where 3 interviews were carried out); 13 life stories, using the photovoice technique with Neets (2 per country, except in Italy where 3 interviews were carried out).</p> <p>The actions with NEETS and children carried out in the project (see deliverable D3.1) are of utmost importance to capture the first-person opinions and feelings of children and NEETS. The PAR approach is perfectly adapted to this purpose.</p>	
WP4	<p>During the period M8-M20, the more active participation of all partners in developing the HUB has been encouraged. In addition to the co-creation actions indicated in Table 1, a monthly follow-up meeting is held with the DG, to gather their opinions, progress, needs, etc.</p>	DG
WP5	<p>Will start on M30</p>	will start on M30
WP6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Teachers have contributed to creating the first promotional video and other communicational material. ◦ Feedback on the efficacy and understandability of graphic materials, newsletters and websites has been collected. ◦ Professionals in the psycho-pedagogical field have contributed to promoting the Let's Care approach in lessons, training, and events attended by a vast target audience. 	DG CoS
WP7	<p>During the period M8-M20, the more active involvement of all partners in ethical and legal issues has been encouraged. For example, in order to carry out all the fieldwork collected in WP3, regular DG meetings have been held, in addition to bilateral meetings with each fieldwork team partner, to adapt the legal templates of consent and data protection to the needs and requirements of each context (country).</p>	DG Fieldwork team
WP8	<p>Specific consultation with the External Ethics Board (EEB) (see Table 1).</p>	EEB

Based on the 7 blocks of indicators included in the PAR manual, an online survey (see Annex IV) has also been carried out among the lead partners of the following WPs: WP1 (CIDALIA), WP2 (UCP), WP3 (COMILLAS), WP7 (COMILLAS), WP8 (COMILLAS), WP4 (FHV), and WP6 (POLO). In addition, a section on future proposals has been included, which will undoubtedly allow us to guide the PAR actions in the project for the coming months. The analysis of the responses to the questionnaire provides us with the following data:

- In all the WP's analysed, Schools (CoS) of the Let's Care project, Schools outside the Let's Care project, Let's Care project stakeholders, Other partners of the Let's Care project Consortium, Stakeholders external to the Let's Care project, and other stakeholders have been involved.
- Participation has been through participatory meetings (with space for opinions, interventions, suggestions, etc.), online training spaces and Face-to-face training spaces.
- In general terms, the contributions of all the entities/individuals that have participated in the WP tasks have been valued.
- The transferability of all WP products analysed was rated as excellent and was one of the most highly rated aspects. An aspect to improve in this respect would be the need to make a greater effort to share the results, which could be one of the aspects to be improved in the future.
- The work packages analysed have been developed in a participatory manner (see Tables 1 and 2). Some ideas for ensuring that the space in which we work is as comfortable and welcoming as possible for participants include:
 - Sometimes, the partners might involve the families in their events, so each of them is responsible for creating a comfortable and welcoming space.
 - We will implement the following strategies: 1. Comfortable Seating; 2. Welcoming Amenities; 3. Good Lighting; 4. Clear Organization

Although partners have not been asked to collect specific information on the qualitative impact of training activities, an internal survey for participants in the national training in Italy has been developed. The results of the training evaluation show a very positive impact on participants. The average score achieved was 4.64 out of 5, indicating high overall satisfaction with the quality of the content and the methodology used. It is particularly noteworthy that almost 70% of respondents gave the highest rating (5), underscoring both the relevance of the training approach and the effectiveness of its implementation. These data are consistent with the participatory and adaptive approach of the LET'S CARE project, validating the added value of the PAR methodology as a tool for fostering commitment and ownership of the process by the communities involved.

This quantitative feedback reinforces the argument that the training component has not only been well received but is also essential to the development of the project. The collaborative structure of the sessions, the use of practical examples and the consistency between the content and the project objectives have been key elements of success. Based on these results, it is recommended to maintain and reinforce the methodological approach used, as well as to expand the qualitative monitoring mechanisms in future sessions to identify specific opportunities for improvement and continue to ensure transformative training aligned with the principles of participatory action research. We will transfer this survey to the other countries for the next implementation period

4. PAR impact

4.1. Social impact

The systematic analysis of stakeholder participation in the LET'S CARE project, using methodologies such as Photovoice, in-depth interviews and training sessions, has provided concrete evidence of the positive impact of the PAR approach. For example, the young NEETs and families involved valued the opportunity to be heard as active agents in educational transformation. Similarly, the results of the training evaluation, with an average score of 4.64 out of 5 and 70% of maximum ratings, reflect high satisfaction among participants and validate the collaborative approach. This information provides a solid basis for affirming that the project has succeeded not only in mobilising but also in empowering the actors involved at all levels.

The project's social impact evaluation is foreseen to be done with KPIs for dissemination, which have only been established for events, not for training. Still, the quantitative impact of the training is set out below and has been included in the progress report.

Table 4. KPIs for events' results

	M1-12		M13-27		TOTAL	
	nr. events	participants	nr. events	participants	nr. events	participants
Training events and workshops	42	4302	145	21136	187	25438
TOTAL	42	4302	145	21136	187	25438

In order to ensure the sustainability and usefulness of the **digital centre (HUB)**, a continuous **monitoring strategy** has been designed that includes monthly meetings with the Driving Group, direct user feedback mechanisms, and iterative co-creation processes for content updating. Accessibility, the representativeness of the materials and the ongoing participation of teachers, families, young people and professionals are the cornerstones of this strategy. The use of the HUB as a living space for sharing good practices, testimonials and tools reflects the project's commitment to the real transfer of knowledge and community revitalisation.

To strengthen the sustainability, impact and practical usefulness of the LET'S CARE project's digital HUB, add-ons (functional complements) have recently been incorporated to enable more effective, real-time monitoring. The suggested add-ons include an integrated analytics module to track content usage, identify the most viewed sections and learn about active user profiles. We are also considering the development of an interactive feedback system that will allow users (teachers, families, students, stakeholders) to evaluate specific resources, suggest improvements and propose new topics. These

add-ons will ensure that the HUB evolves as a living, participatory tool that is aligned with the principles of the project.

The stakeholder impact can be evaluated by: the number of total Hub views (181.175) and total Hub visitors (112.008), number of registered users, number of active users, the number of students, teachers and headmasters involved in the data collection, the number of people that visit each page, the number of the published content, the average views per content.

- Detailed Monitoring Data on the Digital Hub
- Web analytics (with the indicators presented before)
- Concrete evidence of policy engagement

4.2. Political impact

The project has involved political representatives and public policy makers in all phases, with specific interviews, validation of results and active participation in key events. In several countries, interviews with policymakers have created spaces for direct listening on legislative priorities in educational inclusion and have allowed for a progressive alignment between the project's vision and national institutional frameworks. The public policy recommendations to be developed in the next work packages will be the result of this structured and participatory dialogue.

The PMAB has extensively reviewed the LET'S CARE project, delving into its achievements and impacts across technical, economic, and social dimensions. The analysis spans the project's theoretical framework, assessing its implications and effectiveness. Furthermore, the PMAB has examined the project's influence on related deliverables, providing a comprehensive overview of its outcomes and contributions to the field.

The document D1.6 discusses the interaction between policymakers and their involvement in the European LET'S CARE project, aimed at improving educational inclusion and reducing school dropout rates. This project develops a theoretical framework called the "Safe Education Model," which seeks to intervene at individual, relational, community, and political levels. The report includes technical, economic, and social evaluations of the project, as well as feedback from the Policy Makers Advisory Board (PMAB).

PMAB has comprehensively reviewed the LET'S CARE project, looking in depth at its achievements and impacts in the technical, economic and social dimensions. The analysis covers the project's theoretical framework, assessing its implications and effectiveness. In addition, the PMAB has examined the project's influence on the related deliverables, providing an overview of its results and contributions to the field. Thus in D1.6 it has focused the analysis on the interaction between policy makers and their involvement in the European LET'S CARE project. The report included technical,

economic and social assessments of the project, as well as comments from the Policymakers' Advisory Board (PMAB).

The Gender and Diversity Committee (GDC) has been instrumental in ensuring that the principles of inclusion, diversity and co-creation are mainstreamed across all phases of the project. Its involvement has gone beyond technical oversight: it has actively contributed to methodological design, tool validation and continuous feedback, especially in sensitive areas such as the application of gender perspective, diversity and intercultural respect. This sustained participation has ensured that the voice of internal stakeholders is represented continuously and consistently with the project's values. In addition, the GDC has acted as a bridge between the overall project strategy and operational processes, helping to reinforce institutional commitment to the project's objectives. Through its collaboration with the Policy Makers Advisory Board (PMAB), the GDC has promoted critical, conscious and evidence-based implementation of LET'S CARE actions. This integration of diverse perspectives has made it possible to refine monitoring indicators, detect ethical or technical challenges in real time, and propose inclusive adjustments to the project's progress, consolidating its role as a driver of quality, co-responsibility and long-term sustainability. In D1.8 the CDG conducted an Assessment and Application of Gender and Diversity Guidelines and Tools. The main recommendations include: 1. Systematising a gender and diversity monitoring plan. 2. Forming an internal Gender and Diversity Committee. 3. Scheduling regular evaluations of project implementation.

5. Lessons learnt and future recommendations

In order to further improve the application of the PAR approach and co-creation, the following **recommendations** are offered for the further development of the project:

- **WP6:** The project's results should be more efficiently shared with the external audience. There should be a better (and more active) dialogue between WP and Tasks leaders and the WP6 leader to provide clear and on-time ideas of the results obtained in the project. This is particularly important to foster the Hub as a dynamic environment for exchange.
- **WP7:** Introduce structured participatory methods within Technical Meetings, such as co-design workshops or focus groups, to deepen the engagement of all partners. Ensure that these meetings are not only for progress updates but also for active brainstorming and problem-solving, allowing for real-time co-creation of solutions.
- **WP8:** Increase the frequency and depth of EEB consultations to ensure ongoing ethical oversight and integration of diverse ethical perspectives throughout the project lifecycle. Implement a systematic approach to documenting and addressing ethical concerns raised during these discussions, ensuring transparency and accountability in ethical decision-making.

- **WP3** - Collaborative Data Analysis: Engage stakeholders in the data analysis process to ensure their perspectives and insights are incorporated. Organise workshops and feedback sessions where stakeholders can review preliminary findings and contribute to interpreting results.
- **WP4**: Continue to work on an ongoing basis to co-create together new content to be uploaded on the Hub by transforming the requirements into IT technical descriptions.
- **WP6**: The work on T6.5 Policy recommendations and advocacy will be based on PAR. To reinforce communication and dissemination, the partners could ask the teachers more directly to provide suggestions on which training would be useful for them. As mentioned, the training questionnaire implemented in Italy will be implemented in the rest of the countries. Additionally, with regard to the '5 joint events workshops, webinars, round tables, panel presentations with other EU initiatives' in which the PMAB is involved, these will be implemented in the next RP. The current PMAB has been recently established and has been included in deliverable D1.6. For the next period, it will be operating normally once it has been reconfigured. Based on its recommendations and suggestions, they are currently being designed.
- **WP8** - Ethics and Compliance: Conduct ethics training sessions for all team members and stakeholders to ensure understanding and adherence to ethical guidelines.
- **WP3-WP7-WP8** Feedback Mechanisms: Establish structured channels for stakeholders to provide ongoing feedback on all aspects of the WP. Surveys and interviews will be used to gather stakeholder input on the effectiveness of PAR implementation and identify areas for improvement.

6. Conclusions

The PAR approach is necessary to **consider the opinions of the different actors involved in the projects, co-create the results obtained, and** their appropriation. Dissemination, advocacy, and policy action are being developed through the creation of specific infrastructure involving relevant stakeholders at local, national, and international levels, such as public authorities, policymakers, NGOs/civil society, teachers, school leaders, students, parents' associations, and academic institutions, supported by carefully designed co-creation and collaboration mechanisms. The actions with NEETs and children carried out in the project (see deliverable D3.1) are of utmost importance to capture the first-person opinions and feelings of children and NEETs, and the PAR approach is perfectly suited to this purpose. Providing training on these approaches to all project partners facilitates implementation and collective learning to achieve better results, and the interest in these sessions is evidenced by participation in both training sessions. From actions to facts, through these theoretical and practical actions, what is foreseen in the formulation is carried out **theoretically** and contributes to better appropriation and understanding of the project. The monitoring and evaluation

of the PAR approach, based on the indicators of the project's PAR manual, have made it possible to see what **works well and make improvements on what is still needed**. The following results have been achieved by applying the PAR approach in the different WPs: collaboration through participation, participant training, actions evidenced in terms of different outcomes, and the production and acquisition of new knowledge.

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Annex I: PAR dimensions & set of criteria

1. Collaboration

- Who will be involved in conducting this research?
- What roles will they have?
- Do we need to invite outside experts?
- What principles will we agree on when working together?
- How will we work? For example, how frequently do we need to meet, and what will we do between meetings?
- Who will we facilitate meetings with?
- How will we plan the research details? for example,
- We used the '5Ws' can be useful as a way of organising decision-making actions to be taken:
 - WHAT will be done?
 - WHO will be involved?
 - WHERE will it take place?
 - WHEN will each stage happen?
 - HOW will we do this?

2. Knowledge

- What questions are most important?
- What different kinds of knowledge are going to be important?
- What methods do we need to use to find the answers to our research questions?
- What kinds of skills will be needed? Do we have these skills among the group, or do we need to bring in other people to provide help?
- What can each person present contribute to the research process?

3. Power

- Who usually carries out research and makes decisions on issues like the ones we have identified?
- Does our research allow others (outside of the project)? The transferability of knowledge must be present at all times.
- Are those people who are facilitating and involved in the steering group representative of the wider group affected by these issues?
- Are there people who are not represented, who we need to involve in certain stages? If so, how?

- How will we conduct meetings so that everyone is listened to and nobody dominates?
- How will we deal with disagreement, be sure that we don't gloss over differences, but discuss and work through different opinions?

4. Ethics

- Do individuals (or the whole group) want to be anonymous?²
- How are we going to store information in a way that preserves confidentiality?
- How are we going to be accountable?
- How to record what is said and what happens during the research process, from the start?
- Who should get to see this information?
- What are the potential sorts of harm that the research might cause? How can we avoid these?
- What are the potential benefits the research might lead to? How can we maximise these?

5. Building theory

- How will we record discussions, ideas, and the development of the research?
- How will we stand back from time to time to reflect on how the research is going and what has been achieved?
- Who will be involved in analysing the findings, and will everyone understand how this was done?
- Who will be involved in interpreting what the findings mean?
- How will we plan what outputs should be produced from the research?

6. Action

- What changes are needed, according to the research findings—e.g., understanding, behaviour, policy? Deciding on the implications of the research for action is a crucial stage in PAR. Occasionally, a PAR group might agree that no action is needed (for example if the findings show there isn't a problem after all; or everyone agrees that the learning that has taken place during the research is enough).
- Who will do what? Who has the time and ability to get involved in follow-up actions? What resources would help? Should the findings be shared outside of the group for this to take place? Sometimes, the findings will be used only by the group itself. Often, you may want to use them to influence others.

² Only applicable to stakeholders and policymakers; all the rest are anonymous.

- How do we want to share and promote the findings of the research? There are lots of possible modes of disseminating findings, and you should decide which are most appropriate and feasible. For example: a public meeting, a report to policymakers, a press release, a poster campaign, a website, direct changes to practice, advocacy work, further meetings with those responsible or affected by the issue in your research.
- Who could help us to get the messages across and stimulate change?

7. Emotions and well-being

- Is the research topic something that people care passionately about or that directly affects their well-being? In social science research, researchers, depending on the topic, may feel emotionally involved in the research.
- How will we ensure that the space we work in is as comfortable and hospitable as possible for participants?
- How will those involved in meetings deal with negative emotions?
- Might the research affect others outside of the PAR group?
- Do we have backup strategies, such as pointing people to sources of advice for particular problems or counselling services for participants who need them?

Annex II: Infographics

Figure (Annex) 1. PAR Activities LET'S CARE project

Figure (Annex) 2. PAR Methodology goals

Figure (Annex) 3. Let's Care Project: Building Up a Community & PAR Methodology

D1.3 –PAR training manual and infographics on PAR activities during project (2)

Figure (Annex) 4. Training developed

D1.3 –PAR training manual and infographics on PAR activities during project (2)

Brainstorming of topics to be addressed with SMAT methodology	First activity SMAT methodological analysis for children in the first year of primary education (6-7 years). They should analyse the risky situations and/or barriers in the four parts of the mural as explained previously in the presentation. In this case we want to analyse gender perspective in schools.	Wellbeing	risk behaviours
social integration of migrants and ethnic groups		professional qualification	Lowliness
Kindness		Media and self-esteem	Bullying
celebrations with a family	anxiety	attention	Mental health
Dreams: do you think a woman can be president?	Fear of the unknown	Empathy	Hyperactivity
Toys/games/roles for boys and girls	Fear: Kids can experience fear from various things like the unknown, tests, social situations, or physical harm	Gender perspective: boys and girls tend to play different games	take care of animals /people
Favourite colours, clothes	Joys: do you have a dream job?	Focus on Choice and Inclusivity: providing a variety of toys, games, and books that cater to different interests, not just stereotypical boy/girl options. This could include dolls for boys, trucks for girls, art supplies, building blocks. Just an idea :)	Dreams: do you think a man and a woman can have the same type of jobs?
gender based -differences - strength	Motivation to work in order to encourage with a material reward		Dream profession and job
Freedom of Exploration could be joyous: The ability to explore interests and	Sadness: have you ever	Mental health: perhaps try	Fears: do you think women are strong enough to do any kind of job?
toys/games/roies for boys and girls	the unknown, tests, social situations, or physical harm	Focus on Choice and Inclusivity: providing a variety of toys, games, and books that cater to different interests, not just stereotypical boy/girl options. This could include dolls for boys, trucks for girls, art supplies, building blocks. Just an idea :)	What do you want to be when you grow up?
Favourite colours, clothes	Joys: do you have a dream job?		the same type of jobs?
gender based -differences - strength	Motivation to work in order to encourage with a material reward		Dream profession and job
Freedom of Exploration could be joyous: The ability to explore interests and activities freely, regardless of what society typically associates with boys or girls.	Sadness: have you ever wanted to play something but were too afraid of what your colleagues might say?	Mental health: perhaps try to understand how do they feel and what they think it is being ok	Fears: do you think women are strong enough to do any kind of job?
We can combine the toys and the fear. For example, we can ask if they think that people will laugh at them when they see them playing with toys for the opposite gender	Do you feel sad when you lose a game?	Sadness: do you feel sad about having bathrooms for girls and for boys?	What do you want to be when you grow up?
If you could give sadness a taste, what would it taste like and why?	If you could describe sadness as a sound or a song, what would it be and why?	Why do you feel angry when you lose a game?	If you could describe sadness as a color, what would it be and why?
			Would you feel sad if you were prohibited from playing in a boy's team if you were a girl or viceversa?
			Sad: Is there any people who is love me?

D1.3 –PAR training manual and infographics on PAR activities during project (2)

LETS CARE

1 Y 2 PRIMARIA	3 Y 4 PRIMARIA	5 Y 6 PRIMARIA
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cómo aplicar la técnica photovoice o fotovoz con perspectiva de género en la etapa educativa marcada Color de ropa más usado juguetes que tienen profesiones deportes dibujos madres/tias/abuelas que conozcáis que trabajen en algun area científica (Areas STEM) fotos de juegos el papel de las abuelas... Fotos de objetos cotidianos: Un cucharón, una llave inglesa... quién hace qué en la familia (cocinar, comprar, colgar cuadros, hacer chapucillas en casa...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cómo aplicar la técnica photovoice o fotovoz en el estudio y comprensión de niños con movilidad reducida en la etapa educativa marcada niños del cole, familiares... que hayan estado lesionados fotos de calles con barreras arquitectónicas: un bordillo, escaleras... Deportistas, famosos, etc... de movilidad reducida que ejemplifiquen el esfuerzo y la lucha diaria. Historias de mascotas que ayudan a personas con movilidad reducida (DNCE y otros) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cómo aplicar la técnica photovoice o fotovoz con una perspectiva inclusiva con la población migrante Conocer los diversos países, culturas de nuestros compañeros de clase. Famosos que les gusten que sean personas de otro origen étnico/racializados (P.ej Vinicius) Comidas internacionales Foto en la que un alumno se encuentra sólo y los demás están en sus grupos y les preguntaría Juegos tradicionales o populares de diferentes países. Pulseras, ropa, detalles de otros países

Photovoice in classroom?

- Photovoice has been **frequently used with childhood and adolescence** in participatory youth and research projects.
- Belonging to these age groups usually corresponds to the **lack of status and power** to influence the decisions that affect them.
- Photovoice has been **successfully applied with young people** in different contexts, for example, in culturally diverse classrooms, with high school students about their school, with adolescents from multi-ethnic communities, etc.

¿QUÉ ES FOTOVOZ?

Comentarios que es foto voz en general o fotoboyas. Vale, No sé si alguien ha oído hablar de estas metodologías, pero la suerte que tenemos aquí es que vosotras como profesionales de vuestro sector no os va a resultar en absoluto algo ajeno ni algo difícil de implementar por la sencilla razón de que fotovoz Primero, es una herramienta que ya se utiliza en el

Annex III: PAR training presentations

- [June 13, 2023 – Introductory training to the PAR Methodology \(1\)](#)
- [September 19, 2023 – Training to deepen into the PAR Methodology \(2\)](#)
- [December 13, 2023 – Training on the SMAT technique and to build it to measure for the LET’S CARE project from co-creation.](#)
- [December 18, 2023 – Training on the SMAT technique to build measures for the LET’S CARE project from co-creation.](#)
- [January 16, 2024 – Training on the PHOTOVOICE technique and building it to measure for the LET’S CARE project from co-creation.](#)
- [January 22, 2024 – Training on the PHOTOVOICE technique and building it to measure for the LET’S CARE project from co-creation.](#)
- [January 24, 2024 – Training on the PHOTOVOICE technique and building it to measure for the LET’S CARE project from co-creation.](#)
- [March 5, 2024 – Training on the SMAT technique to build measures for the LET’S CARE project from co-creation.](#)
- [May 28, 2024 – Photovoice Return session. To present the results obtained through the photovoice technique.](#)

Annex IV: On-line questionnaire

The screenshot shows a web-based survey titled "LET'S CARE PAR SURVEY 2024". The header includes the "Let's care" logo and the title. The main content area is dark teal and contains the following text:

The LETS CARE project has the PAR approach as a cross-cutting orientation in its different actions.

Participatory Action Research (PAR) is collaborative research, education and action used to gather information to change social or environmental issues. In PAR, people concerned or affected by a problem take a leading role in the production and use of knowledge about it.

The aim of this questionnaire is to find out how the LET'S CARE PAR toolkit, developed in June 2023, has been applied over the last year (June 2023-June 2024). Only the operational WPs during this period have been taken into account for the form. When answering, please think about the actions developed with a PAR approach during this period only (1 June 2023-30 June 2024).

The answers will be processed and analysed and included in the Deliverable D1.3 "PAR training manual and infographics on PAR activities during Project".

It is necessary that at least one person from each WP lead partner is able to fill in this form. The PAR approach is transversal throughout all WP and LETS CARE tasks so all lead partners should collect the necessary information from their WP(s) to fill in this questionnaire.

It will take less than 10 minutes. The deadline for completion is 15 July (inclusive).

Thank you very much for your cooperation

* Obligatorio

WP & Task

1. Partner's name

- CID (WP1)
- UCP (WP2)
- COM (WP3, WP6, WP7, WP8)
- FHV (WP4)
- POLO (WP6)

[Siguiente](#)

No revele nunca su contraseña. [Notificar abuso](#)

Microsoft 365

Figure (Annex) 5. PAT online questionnaire